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Research Article

INCIDENCE OF INFECTIONS DUE TO H. PYLORI AMONG PATIENTS OF CHRONIC URTICARIA & BACTERIUM IMPACTS ON ITS COURSE

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Abstract:

Objective: The aim of this research work is to find out the occurrence of infection of helicobacter pylori in the patients suffering from ICU (Idiopathic Chronic Urticaria) & to observe if the abolition of the bacterium impacts the urticaria's course.

Methodology: Total 100 patients suffering ICU & forty-three healthy females with matched in age and gender faced the serological examination for the infection of helicobacter pylori. We examined all the patients suffering from ICU for the infection of H. pylori with 13 C-urea tests as well as various tests of serology. We obtained the gastric biopsy from thirty-six patients. Patients with confirmed diagnosis of the infection of H. pylori were under treatment for complete two weeks. After completing six weeks, we tested all the patients for infection of H. pylori and we assessed their urticaria clinically.

Results: We found no important disparity in the occurrence of infection due to helicobacter pylori between patients suffering from ICU & healthy controls. Seventy-six percent patients were available with the infection of H. pylori and 69.80% healthy controls were also facing the same issue. Out of total seventy-six treated patients, only twenty-four patients displayed comprehensive decrease of urticaria after the abolition of the infection of H. pylori, other patients showed a little improvement in some of the symptoms.

Conclusion: The patients suffering from the ICU were available with the high frequencies of infections due to helicobacter pylori as healthy controls. There is a strong association of the bacterium eradication with the improvement of the symptoms of urticaria, signifying a probable part of the H. pylori in the development of this disease of skin complication.

Key Words: Helicobacter, Frequencies, Urticarial, H. Pylori, Abolition.

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INTRODUCTION:

Urticaria is very frequent disease that is always a serious challenge to the skin specialist because of its evasive causes of disease. This disease is a reason of severe social, professional, personal and economical incapacity comparable with that linked with the serious diseases of heart [1]. Urticaria is very common disease of the skin, with a rate of prevalence of ranging from 1.20% to 23.0% [2]. In majority of patients, there is not the detection of the disease even after intensive examination [3]. There are many factors linked with the development of the disease of urticarial as focal infections, allergy from food or medicines, atopy, diseases of auto-immunity & many others [4, 5].

Current interrogations highlighted the possible part of the infection of helicobacter pylori on the upper GI (Gastro-intestinal) tract as a probable reason in the complication of ICU. This research work carried out to find out the rate of incidence of infection of H. pylori in the patients suffering from ICU & evaluate the effectualness of the abolition of the infection of helicobacter pylori on the diseases of skin.

METHODOLOGY:

The duration of this research work was from March 2017 to April 2019 at Jinnah Hospital Lahore. Total 100 patients suffering from ICU in which sixty-two were female and thirty males were the part of this research work. The range of the age of patients was from fourteen to sixty-three years with an average age of 42.70 years. The average duration of the disease was 36.20 months. There were forty-three healthy controls with age and sex match in which twenty-eight were females and fifteen were males. History & clinical results diagnosed the presence of the disease of ICU. The patients suffering from other serious complications were not the part of this research work.

13 C urea breath test was in use for the examination of the infection of H. pylori [6, 7] & ELISA was in use for the particular IgG antibodies against the helicobacter pylori [8, 9]. If the results of both of the tests were positive, we proposed the gastroscopy & mucosal biopsies for those patients. We informed all the patients completely about the features of we obtained the written consent from all the participants of the research work. We conducted the serological testing of the healthy controls for the infection of the helicobacter pylori in the start of the research work to evaluate the occurrence of the incidence of the helicobacter pylori in normal general population of our country. We scheduled a treatment of two weeks with different quantities of amoxicillin, clarythromycin & pantoprazole for the patients suffering infections of helicobacter pylori as diagnosed by both tests. We assessed the severity of the ICU after six weeks of treatment. We performed the statistical analysis with the utilization of Chi square test. If the complete reduction of the urticaria was the outcome within 2 weeks, it was the complete remission.

RESULTS:

The research group & the group of control were comparable regarding age (42.70 versus 44.20 years) & gender (62.0% versus 65.0% females). The test of urease breath & antibodies of IgG against helicobacter pylori were positive in eighty-seven patients (87.0%) & seventy-six patients (76.0%) correspondingly in the group of ICU patients. Of seventy-six patients with diagnosed infection of helicobacter pylori, total thirty-six patients accepted the process of endoscopy, and demonstration of the helicobacter pylori carried out with the examination of histology. Of forty-three healthy controls, 69.80% (n: 30) found with the positive IgG serology (Table-1).

Category		Patients		Controls	
		No	Percent	No	Percent
Urease test	(+)	87	87	-	-
	(-)	13	13	-	-
IgG	(+)	76	76	30	69.8
	(-)	24	24	13	30.2
Total		100	100	43	-

We treated the seventy-six patients for the abolition of the infection of helicobacter pylori with positive tests. We examined the patients for complete six weeks after the completion of the treatment for fourteen days. We got the proper eradication of helicobacter pylori in sixty-eight patients. Of these patients, only 32.40% (n: 22) found with complete reduction (eleven patients got recovery in just seven days); 42.60% (n: 29) patients

found with partial reduction and 25.0% (n: 17) patients displayed no alteration in the disease of skin. Among twenty-four patients who did not obtain therapy because they negative for the helicobacter pylori, five patients displayed some degree of improvement (two patients showed complete reduction & three displayed partial decrease) & nineteen patients showed no change in their disease (Table-2)

Table-II: Idiopathic Chronic Urticaria after Treatment for Helicobacter Pylori Infection

Category	Complete remission		Partial remission		No change		Total
	No	Percent	No	Percent	No	Percent	
Treated Group	22.00	32.40	29.00	42.60	17.00	25.00	68.00
Untreated Group	2.00	8.30	3.00	12.50	19.00	79.20	24.00
Treated Not Eradicated	2.00	25.00	3.00	37.50	3.00	37.50	8.00
Total	26.00	65.70	35.00	92.60	39.00	141.70	100.00

DISCUSSION:

Traditionally, urticaria is the almost daily routine incidence of the urticarial wheals for minimum six weeks [10]. The main reasons of the cause of this disease are not clear. There are different factors which can be the causative factors for the development of this disease as some medicines, additives, some physical factors & some diseases of the internal human body [3-5]. This term of ICU is in common use in conditions in which urticarial vasculitis & leading physical urticarias have got exclusion [11]. ICU has caused to impact at least 0.10% population [11, 12] & it has a complete relapsing course, with about 20.0% patients still acquiring the disease after complete ten years [3]. Recent proofs state that majority of instances of the urticaria are auto-immune & from 27.0% to 5.0% patients suffering from ICU are available to have functional auto-antibodies engaged against the alpha-chain of the high-affinity receptor of IgE or low frequent against IgG [10, 13, 14].

Some current research works stated the *H. pylori* infections as the most important in the development of the disease of ICU [15-18]. But some research works were against this relationship [19-21]. *Helicobacter pylori*, a gram negative bacteria, which can be main factor of the development of the disease especially gastric complications like peptic ulcer [22] & gastric carcinomas [23], has found with association with different extra diseases of digestions [24]. *Helicobacter pylori* is the most probable reason behind Henoch Schonlein purpura [25], Sweet's Syndrome [26], rosacea [27, 28] & Sjogren's syndrome [29].

There are no much research works about the occurrence of the infection of *H. pylori* in our population. We used the control group in this research work and in this research work, we discovered a high occurrence of *H. pylori* infection in our general population (69.80%). Most of the patients of this research work got improvement after the successful treatment against the infection of the *H. pylori*, only 32.40% patients displayed complete reduction in the disease after the decrease in the symptoms of urticarial. Some other research works also reported the same findings [18, 19]. Most of the research works from West provides rates of remission from 95.0% to hundred percent having infection of *helicobacter pylori* [15-17]. The inconsistency between those findings & ours results was due to research works conducted with very less occurrence of the infection of *helicobacter pylori* (30.0% to 40.0%) [30], in comparison with the occurrence rate of this research work (69.80%).

CONCLUSION:

The occurrence of the infection of *H. pylori* is very high in the patients of ICU, we achieved complete reduction in very less patients after the abolition of the bacterium, signifying a probable part of few patients of infection of *H. pylori* in spread of some complications of skin. There is recommendation of the further controlled with random population to consolidate the findings of this research work.

REFERENCES:

1. Juhlin L. Recurrent urticaria: clinical investigation of 330 patients. *Br J Dermatol* 1981; 104(4): 369-81.
2. Eggers RH, Kulp A, Tegeler R, et al. A methodological analysis of the 13C-urea breath test for detection of *Helicobacter pylori* infections: high sensitivity and specificity within 30 min using 75mg of 13C-urea. *Eur J Gastroenterol* 1990; 2:437-44.
3. Vaira D, Holton J, Menegatti M, et al. New immunological assays for the diagnosis of *Helicobacter pylori* infection. *Gut* - 1999; 45 Suppl 1: I23-7.
4. Herbrink P, van Doorn LJ. Serological methods for diagnosis of *Helicobacter pylori* infection and monitoring of eradication therapy. *Eur J Clin Microbiol Infect Dis* 2000; 19(3): 164-73.
5. Greaves MW. Chronic urticaria. *J Allergy Clin Immunol* 2000; 105: 664-72.
6. Greaves MW. Chronic urticaria. *N Engl J Med* 1995; 332:1767-72.
7. O'Donnell BF, Lawlor F, Simpson J, et al. The impact of chronic urticaria on quality of life. *Br J Dermatol* 1997; 136:197-201.
8. Champion RH, et al. Investigation and management of chronic urticaria and angioedema. *Clin Exp Dermatol* 1982; 7:291.
9. Hellgren L. The prevalence of urticaria in the total population. *Acta Allergol* 1972; 27:236-40.
10. Tong LJ, Balakrishnan G, Kochan JP, et al. Assessment of autoimmunity in patients with chronic urticaria. *J Allergy Clin Immunol* 1997; 99(4): 461-65.
11. Wisniewski RM, Peura DA. *Helicobacter pylori*: beyond peptic ulcer disease. *Gastroenterologist* 1997; 5:295-305.
12. Champion RH. Acute and chronic urticaria. *Semin Dermatol* 1987; 6: 286-91.
13. Sabroe RA, Seed PT, Stat C, et al. Chronic idiopathic urticaria: Comparison of the clinical features of patients with & without anti-FcepsilonRI or anti-IgE autoantibodies. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 1999; 40: 443-50.

14. Dooley CP, Cohen H, Fitzgibbons PL, et al. Prevalence of Helicobacter pylori infection and histologic gastritis in asymptomatic persons. *N Engl J Med* 1989;321: 1562-6.
15. Reinauer S, Megahed M, Goerz G, et al. Schönlein-Henoch purpura associated with gastric Helicobacter pylori infection. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 1995; 33:876-9.
16. Champion RH, Roberts SOB, Carpenter RG, Roger JH. Urticaria and angioedema. A review of 554 patients. *Br J Dermatol* 1969; 81:588-97.
17. Tebbe B, Geilen CC, Schulzke JD, et al. Helicobacter pylori infection and chronic urticaria. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 1996; 34(4): 685-6.
18. Nazif Kurkcuoglu. Sweet's syndrome associated with Helicobacter pylori infection. *J Am Acad Dermatol*. 1997; 37(1): 124-25.
19. Wedi B, Wagner S, Werfel T, et al. Prevalence of Helicobacter pylori-associated gastritis in chronic urticaria. *Int Arch Allergy Immunol*, 1998; 116(4): 288-94.
20. Di Campli C, Gasbarrini A, Nucera E, et al. Beneficial Effects of Helicobacter pylori Eradication on Idiopathic Chronic Urticaria. *Dig Dis Sci* 1998; 43: 1226-9.
21. Wustlich S, Brehler R, Luger TA, et al. Helicobacter pylori as a possible bacterial focus of chronic urticaria. *Dermatology* 1999; 198(2): 130-2.
22. Valsecchi R, Pigatto P. Chronic urticaria and Helicobacter pylori. *Acta Derm Venereol*, 1998; 78(6): 440-2.
23. Liutu M, Kalimo K, Uksila J, et al. Etiologic aspects of chronic urticaria. *Source Int J Dermatol*, 1998; 37(7): 515-9.
24. Schnyder B, Helbling A, Pichler WJ. Chronic idiopathic urticaria: natural course and association with Helicobacter pylori infection. *Int Arch Allergy Immunol* 1999; 119(1): 60-3.
25. Graham DY. Campylobacter pylori and peptic ulcer disease. *Gastroenterology* 1989; 96:615-25.
26. Kelly SM, Geraghty JM, Neale G. H. pylori, gastric carcinoma & MALT lymphoma. *Lancet* 1994; 1:343-418.
27. Utas S, Ozbakir O, Turasan A, Utas C. Helicobacter pylori eradication treatment reduces the severity of rosacea. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 1999; 40:433-5.
28. Rebora A, Drago F, Picciotto A. Helicobacter pylori in patients with rosacea. *Am J Gastroenterol* 1994; 89:1603-4.
29. Figura N, Giordano N, Burrioni D, et al. Sjogren's syndrome and Helicobacter pylori infection. *Eur J Gastroenterol Hepatol* 1994; 6:321-2.
30. Graham DY, Klein PD, Evans DR Jr, et al. Campylobacter pylori detected non-invasively by the ¹³C-urea breath test. *Lancet* 1987; 1:1174-7.